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PARADOX OF POPULAR CULTURE. “Popular culture is a contradiction in terms. If it is popular, it is not culture.” – Vivienne Westwood

The word "popular culture" was first used to describe the cultural practices and beliefs of the 'general public' in England in the middle of the 19th century, in contrast to the cultural activities and ideas of the elite or aristocracy. If we take a close look at the term "Popular Culture", "popular" has a commercialising aspect as it is a global phenomenon whereas "culture" derives from the Latin word "colere" which means "cultivation," indicating organic growth. Thus, the claim made by Vivienne Westwood "Popular culture is a contradiction in terms." The statement "If it is popular, it is not culture" calls for a reevaluation of the relation between cultural relevance and popularity. Her assertion provokes thoughtful consideration of the idea of culture, the dynamics of popularity, and the relationship between the two. Westwood seems to be implying that real culture can only exist outside of the popular domain. A more nuanced view, on the other hand, reveals the challenges of both making and consuming cultural expressions. Westwood's claim makes us to question if the authenticity of culture is always diminished because of their popularity. To accommodate mass consumption, cultural artefacts may occasionally be commodified and lose their original importance. This process, which is also known as "cultural commodification," can cause cultural forms to become homogenised and commercialised, which lowers their artistic or ideological worth.

One example of cultural dilution is the widespread production of mass-produced goods based on famous artworks or cultural icons. Things that formerly held cultural meaning could be reduced to nothing more than commodities and lose their connection to historical or symbolic contexts. Because of this commodification, authenticity may be compromised in favour of commercial gain and broad appeal, leading to a superficial grasp of culture. Here we can cite the example of Angaraag Mahanta's (stagename, Papon) and Niniola's (Nigerian songwriter and singer) song *Ibaasi* which is a fusion of Assamese Bihu Folk song with some Nigerian and English lyrics in it. They are also seen using electric guitar and drums which are not a part of Bihu and thus losing its "essence". They have altered Bihu's original "form" in order to showcase it on a worldwide scale, which has led to its commercialization. Adorno and Horkheimer too points out the commodification of art in their work *Dialectic of Enlightenment* (1947). They contend that the mass media, entertainment, and other sectors of popular culture, together with the cultural industry, sustain a homogenised and commercialised culture that advances capitalism's goals and upholds social conformity. Again, exclusivity is apparent when discussing "popular" culture. "Othering" of the people by "The Popular" is what Richard Middleton talks about in his essay *LOCATING THE PEOPLE Music and the Popular*. "The Popular" subjugates and marginalises the others. Here, there is also the issue of who exactly qualifies as "The Popular." Within this framework, who is in charge? The idea of hegemony by Antonio Gramsci is echoed here. Let us take the example of the Satriya dance from Assam. This classical dance which forms an integral symbol of the culture of Assam, is not as 'popular' as Bharatnatyam, which is even

performed by the people of Assam. This is again an indication of how Northeastern States (like Assam) are marginalised by the “mainland” India.

But to write off all popular culture phenomena as lacking in cultural value is an oversimplification. Many works of culture have become widely popular while maintaining their creative integrity and making a significant contribution to society. Consider the genre of reggae music. Having originated in Jamaica in the late 1960s, reggae music has evolved to become a global symbol of spirituality, resistance, and unity. Artists such as Bob Marley and Peter Tosh have popularized its theme of love, emancipation and justice. Reggae music is still rooted in Jamaican culture, Rastafarian ideals, and advocates for the sufferings of underprivileged groups despite its commercial success. Another example is Manga and Anime. Manga and anime, which have their roots in Japan, have spread throughout the world and influenced popular culture, art, and storytelling through their unique visuals, intricate plots, and themes reflecting Japanese society and their culture. Despite their globalized success, they maintain their cultural essence.

Furthermore, in modern society, the lines separating high culture from popular culture are becoming increasingly hazy. Traditional hierarchies of taste are questioned when cultural borders grow more inclusive and new kinds of cultural creation are born. For example, best-selling books like *Harry Potter* are brought into academic settings, refuting the idea that popular fiction cannot be regarded as highbrow literature. The rise of internet culture, where social media trends, viral videos, and memes influence speech and collective awareness, further demonstrate this shift. Digital technologies democratise cultural creation by opening up cultural platforms to people from different backgrounds. This has thus, contributed to the democratisation of cultural output too. Traditional cultural gatekeepers have been overthrown by this democratisation, giving marginalised voices a platform, changing cultural narratives. Social media movements with hashtags like #MeToo and #BlackLivesMatter sparked debate across the world by promoting the voices of the marginalized and challenging the inequalities.

Given these intricacies, it is clear that the link between culture and popularity is not a straightforward but complicated and dynamic one. Popular culture has the power to reflect and influence society's ideals, goals, and struggles, even though it can occasionally err towards commercialism and superficiality. We must critically interact with popular culture phenomena considering its underlying power relations as both the consumers and creators. Ultimately, Vivienne Westwood's assertion, despite its seeming extremeness, emphasises how crucial it is to critically assess how power, consumerism, and cultural production are related.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Horkheimer, Max and Theodor W. Adorno. "The Culture Industry: Enlightenment as Mass Deception". *Dialectic of Enlightenment*, edited by Gunzelin Schmid Noeri, Redwood City: Stanford University Press, 2002, pp.94-136.
- Middleton, Richard. "Locating the People: Music and the Popular." *The Cultural Study of Music*, edited by Martin Clayton, Trevor Herbert, and Richard Middleton, Routledge, 2003, pp. 251-262.
- Gramsci, Antonio. Selections from the *Prison Notebooks* of Antonio Gramsci. New York: International Publishers, 1971.

<https://youtu.be/E8snXfSce70?si=lyR9ydrmm3ul2UO9>